

THE PLACE AND IMPORTANCE OF PRESUPPOSITION IN A LITERATURE TEXT

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Annotation: This article provides a detailed explanation of the concept of presupposition, its role and significance in a literary text, and information about the literary text and the essence of presupposition.

Key words: presupposition, pragmatic phenomenon, semantic concept, hidden information, textual implicature, context, literary text.

Currently, in the field of pragmalinguistics, as in all areas of world linguistics, the number of studies is increasing, the scale of achievements and innovations is increasing. In particular, the analysis of a literary text from a pragmalinguistic point of view, the identification of its efficiency factors, the analysis of the relationship of the author's intention to the person, speech situation, communicative strategy, etc., sheds light on the pragmatic aspects of the language.

It is important to note that the essence of presupposition and literary text is their common ontological (doctrine of being, philosophical) feature, which determines their consideration within the framework of a general study in order to determine their mutual relationship and interaction, although they relate to phenomena (event, fact) belonging to different categories: presupposition is a concept, and literary text is a unit. According to I.R. Galperin, "most of the interpretation of a work of art is based on presupposition, especially linguocultural presupposition", which serves as a determinant of the text as a category of cognitive activity. Presuppositional text signs that make up the linguocognitive complex of a literary text represent a three-level system, in which units of lower structural levels are combined into units of higher levels, performing a certain task. A literary text is a form of realization of human existence through language, a form of realization of the human self. In the pragmatic analysis of a literary text, the speech of the author and characters, their purpose, means of expressing pragmatic meaning, in particular, pragmatic presupposition, play an important role. Therefore, a literary text is distinguished from other types of text by a strong expression of emotional-expressiveness, the ability of the depicted reality to affect the reader's feelings, to arouse them, to form a positive or negative position. One of the factors affecting the ability of a literary text to realize its interactive capabilities and solve communicative problems is the phenomenon of presupposition, which has the functional form of motivational factors of a literary text. A text is a unit of the highest level of the

syntactic level of language, a structurally, semantically, and communicatively coherent whole that arises in oral and written form based on the coherence of a sequence of sentences.

Presupposition, like a literary text, is a multifaceted concept that does not have a general classification and definition. The first studies of this phenomenon appeared more than a century ago in the scientific works of G. Frege, who understood presupposition as part of a sentence in the form of a judgment about the truth of the existence of the denotation, which is an indispensable condition for addressing the truth value of the sentence.

The phenomenon of presupposition is of great importance for the content of the text, and is considered a reminder of the speaker's and listener's prior knowledge, information related to the content of the text and connected in content with it. In the process of presenting information about the subject of the text, it is necessary to refer to information that has been previously reported or is expected to be reported. Through this phenomenon, such goals as clarifying information, addressing previous or expected information, developing the stated idea, and substantiating it are realized.

According to N. Mahmudov, any text is formally condensed and shortened according to presuppositions. If the presuppositions of the economy of language means, which is the leading trend in language development, are formally described, then the text increases in size. This is necessarily done in cases where the reader is not familiar with the topic of speech, that is, the presuppositions related to the same speech are explicitly described one after another. Literary texts encourage their reader to think more. Presuppositional units, that is, the content given in a hidden way at the lexical, morphological or syntactic level, force the reader to guess for himself. This ensures a deep dialogue between the reader and the text.

Presuppositions create the context of the text and help the reader to correctly understand the events. Hidden meanings in speech help to understand the general content of the text, the reader correctly interprets events through not directly stated, but implied meanings. The analysis can be complete only when the national characteristics reflected in the literary text are taken into account. In the literary text, auxiliary word groups are considered presuppositional tools. Relatives came in and wanted to see the patient, but the doctor allowed only three people. Presupposition: He did not allow other people. "Other people also wanted to come in." (A. Qahhor "Orphan")

This meaning is not directly stated, but the reader understands this meaning

only through its implication. Such presuppositional tools serve not only to understand the story, but also to reflect the state of the characters, the restrictions in the environment, and social relations.

These ideas are based on a modern pragmatic approach to analyzing a literary text. That is, in addition to the meaning directly conveyed by the words in the text, the hidden information behind them is also important. Presuppositions encourage the reader to think actively, allowing them to delve deeper into the text.

In addition, presuppositions that arise through loading, linking, or tone are an expression of the author's skillful absorption of hidden content through the text. This makes the literary text deeper and more multilayered.

Presupposition is a very important pragmatic phenomenon in a literary text, through which the author conveys his idea to the reader not directly, but indirectly, in a hidden way. This makes the text multilayered, impressive, and rich in content. It forms the inner meaning of the text. With the help of presuppositions, the writer often conveys hidden information that is not directly stated, but must be understood by the reader. "Anwar lied again." Presupposition: Anwar has lied before.

Presupposition serves to reveal the psyche of the characters. The character's inner state, thoughts, or attitude is not expressed, but is revealed through the form of the sentence or choice of words. "Did I yell at them?" In this sentence, the character is justifying himself, in fact, he did yell, but regrets it. Internal suffering is revealed through presupposition.

Presuppositions enrich the text with ambiguity and complexity, which arouses surprise, contemplation, and aesthetic pleasure in the reader. The writer creates artistic sophistication by speaking indirectly, not directly.

In a literary text, presupposition is a hidden but effective level of meaning through which the writer:

- Increases the ideological depth of the work;
- Reveals the character's psyche, inner world;
- Encourages the reader to think, activates his thinking;
- Introduces artistic richness to the text;
- Indirectly conveys the writer's idea;
- Adds depth and aesthetic pleasure to the text

A literary text without presuppositions can often be simplified, superficial, and less aesthetically impressive. Therefore, this pragmatic device performs an important semantic function in literature.

A literary text is not only a means of reflecting reality, but also an aesthetic and pictorial structure that penetrates the deep layers of human thinking. The phenomenon of presupposition also plays a significant role in the formation of pragmatic content in a literary text. Presuppositions represent information and ideas that are hidden in the meaning and context of the text, but are important, therefore they further expand the meaning of the literary text, play an important role in conveying a moderate meaning in the text. From a systematic point of view, presupposition is considered as a common fund of linguistic, cultural and extralinguistic knowledge, which is part of the cognitive part of the author and the reader and is perceived in the field of a literary text in the form of presuppositional text signs. From a functional point of view, presupposition is considered as a means of directing the author and the reader to the cognitive-emotional space of a literary text. Based on the above considerations, we can say that presupposition is a hidden communication between the author and the reader. Through this tool, the author secretly instills his idea, and the reader actively participates in the process of comprehending it. Thus, presupposition makes the literary text deeper, more complex and aesthetically richer.

Presuppositions in the text create a connection with previous events, hidden reasons or the socio-cultural environment. The text becomes holistic, logically connected and consistent. Presuppositions force the reader to understand the text more deeply and find the hidden meaning. The reader participates not as a passive, but as an active interpreter. The author conveys his social, moral or philosophical position not directly, but in a hidden way. Since the reader discovers the idea himself, he perceives it more effectively and deeply.

Thus, in a literary text, presupposition is not only a linguistic phenomenon, but also a means of aesthetic and philosophical understanding, one of the main strategies for conveying the writer's artistic intention to the reader. In this regard, it is necessary to study presupposition as a communicative-pragmatic tool that constitutes a deep layer of a literary text.

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